

Interface strengthening mechanisms of Ti/CFRP fiber metal laminate after adding MWCNTs to resin matrix

Hao Wang, Kai Jin, Jie Tao

Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics

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Introduction to fiber metal laminates

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Fiber Metal Laminates (FMLs) :

A hybrid laminates stacked by alternate metal and FRP layers

Anti-fatigue

Anti-flaming

Anti-impact

Anti-corrosion

Introduction to fiber metal laminates

Application

- Boeing Co. : 757 和 777 cabin floor panel, first commercial application
- Airbus Co. : A380 fuselage skin, **25.9% weight reduction for 280 dollar per kilogram saved weight**

A380: The most advanced airframe (examples)

Glare 27 pieces, 470m², weight ↓ 800kg

Weight ↓ 25~30%
Fatigue life ↑ 1,000%

Introduction to fiber metal laminates

Application

- **Aircraft**

- **Rail transit**

- **Automobile**

- **Others**

Introduction to fiber metal laminates

Metal surface treatment

However, few researchers tried to bind the metal/resin interface through additive.

Introduction to Carbon nanotubes(CNTs)

- High aspect ratio
- High mechanical strength
- High electrical properties

Application

- Composite Materials
- Coatings and Films
- Microelectronics
- Biotechnology
- Energy Storage and Environment

Methods

Reveal the mechanism of interfacial strengthening after adding MWCNTs to resin matrix

Molecular dynamics analysis

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

Build the CNT model

Armchair (6,6) Carbon nanotubes with wall numbers 1-6

Zigzag (10,0) Carbon nanotubes with wall numbers 1-6

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

Build interface model

PMR Ti

Molecular dynamics simulation results

Effect of MWCNT types on the interface performance

- Affect the morphology
- Improving contact area of the polyimide on the titanium surface
- The contact area added the armchair CNT larger than zigzag system

Molecular dynamics simulation results

Effect of MWCNT types on the interface performance

Average surface energy of the last 20 frames

$$\Delta E_{Ti\&PI} = E_{Ti_PI} - (E_{Ti} + E_{PI})$$

- The type and the wall number have a great influence on interfacial properties
 - For improving the interface performance: the armchair CNT was better than the zigzag CNT
 - Zigzag CNT, the tube numbers \uparrow , interface performance \downarrow , 4 walls tend to be stable
 - Armchair CNT, 3 walls, the interface effect was enhanced by 81.3% VS no CNT system, VS zigzag CNT system increased by 34.3%
 - Walls exceeds 3, the enhancement effect decreases and tends to stabilize, as the number of walls increases
- So the 3 walls armchair carbon tube was used to analyze the reinforcement mechanism.

Mechanism of MWCNTs on the interface strengthening

Molecular dynamic adsorption process interface model
(0wt% and 5wt% MWCNTs)

■ PI ■ Ti ■ MWCNT

- A few PI molecules were adsorbed on the Ti surface
- Adsorbed on the outer wall of the tube
- Helix in the outer wall of MWCNT
- PI molecules stacked on each other

Mechanism of MWCNTs on the interface strengthening

◆ Van der Waals

◆ H-O Hbond

◆ π - π bond

PI Ti PI MWCNT

- The main attraction of PI molecules on MWCNTs and Ti surfaces were based on van der Waals forces
- In the Ti-PI-MWCNTs system, the PI molecules were adsorbed helix on the MWCNTs surface under the action of π - π bonding
- The Van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonds driving the PI molecules stacked with each other.

Interface shear simulation

Total potential energy during shear simulation: (a) 0wt% MWCN and (b) 5wt% MWCNT

$$G_S = \frac{E_{max} - E_{min}}{A}$$

**Fracture energy: 352.8KJ/m² (0wt% MWCNTs),
1504KJ/m² (5wt% MWCNTs).**

Macroscopic experimental

Interface shear experiment

Specimen preparation

Single lap Shear test

The maximum force (P_{max}) was used to calculate the interfacial fracture energy (G_E) of the Ti/CFRP using Eq.

$$G_E = \frac{P_{max}^2}{E_{Ti} t_{Ti} b_{Ti}^2 + E_{CFRP} t_{CFRP} b_{CFRP}^2}$$

(a) Represents the ILSS specimen ; (b) The mechanical tests set up of ILSS test fixture

Interface shear experiment results

Failure morphology of the interface:
(a) 0wt% MWCNTs; (b) 5wt% MWCNTs

- Without MWCNTs delaminated with a large gap. In contrast, the gap of delamination is not very big.
- arrow 1 represents pulled out
arrow 2 represents fracture,
followed by MWCNT's own fracture,
and pull-out failure consuming energy
- Shear failure mode ➡ cohesive failure

Interface shear experiment results

Comparison of MD simulated fracture energy and experimental fracture energy

- Experimental values were higher than simulation results.

Because of the treated rough surface of Ti sheet, there is a mechanical interlocking effect.

- But the trends were consistent.

● $G_{E \text{ MWCNT}}$ VS $G_{E \text{ without}}$, ↗ 500%

- The added MWCNTs improved shear resistance effectively

**Effect of MWCNTs
orientation on the interface
strengthening**

Effect of MWCNTs orientation on the interface strengthening

The MWCNTs angle affected the adsorption form and quantity of PI molecules on the interface

Effect of MWCNTs orientation on the interface strengthening

The O atom density cloud map of PI molecules on Ti surface

0wt% E_{inter} -328.4Kcal/mol,
5wt% E_{inter} -512.8Kcal/mol

If MWCNTs paralleled to the Ti layer, resulting in the minimum interfacial strength.

At 90°, yielding best interface binding performance.

Conclusions

The armchair type carbon tube has better effect on the interface compatibility than the zigzag type, and the 3 walls CNT was the better. It was found from MD analysis that a few PI moleculars were partially stacked and adsorbed on Ti layer and most PI molecules were adsorbed on the MWCNTs surface. The van der Waals force was the main driving force for adsorption of PI molecular. The PI molecules were entangled on MWCNTs surfaces under the action of π - π bond. Meanwhile, the presence of H-O hydrogen bonds promoted the absorption.

It has been proved that the addition of MWCNTs to the PI resin matrix do improve the strength of Ti/CFRP interface. The MWCNTs as bridges can connect the Ti and the PI resin. No matter whether MWCNTs pull out or fracture, there were always some resins left on the MWCNTs and the Ti surface. The failure mode changed from interface failure to cohesive failure due to the addition of MWCNTs to the resin primer layer.

When positioning MWCNTs at different orientations, the structure of the Ti-PI-MWCNTs ternary system was radically changed. The MWCNTs angle affected the adsorption form and quantity of PI molecules on the interface. The most PI molecules were present on the Ti layer surface at 90° , yielding best interface binding performance. On the contrary, if MWCNTs paralleled to the Ti layer, the interfacial interaction energy was the lowest, resulting in the minimum interfacial strength.

南京航空航天大学

*Nanjing University of
Aeronautics and Astronautics*

Professor JieTao

research group

Thank you !

Website: www.taojiegrounuaa.edu.cn

E-mail: taojie@nuaa.edu.cn